

ASSESSING RESILIENCE AMONG EMERGING ADULTS DURING COVID 19

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Abstract

Globally, COVID 19 pandemic has caused a huge amount of stress among the population. The stress of unprecedented times has led negative impact on the psychological health, social, and emotional well-being of the individuals. During tough times of uncertainty, the support and confidence from the immediate family members, works like wonder with dealing the unfavorable circumstances and eventually motivates us to bounce back from the challenging situations. The present research paper focuses on the concept of resilience among emerging adults during the pandemic COVID 19. Brief Resilience Scale (Smith et al, 2008) was used to assess the resilience among the respondents, the online link for the scale was shared via Google form and it was substantiated by telephonic interview with 36 emerging adults. The respondents of the study were having diverse background such as some pursuing higher studies, and others were working professionals who were either working from their own homes or from rented apartments. The emerging adults were living with their families and alone in temporary housing and were in the age group of 18-25 years. Brief Resilience Scale indicated that a major proportion of the respondents had a medium level (58.33%) of resilience followed by the individuals with low resilience (36.11%) and very few (5.55%) with high resilience. Additionally, respondents with low level of resilience were especially the ones who were living alone during the pandemic.

Keywords: resilience, emerging adults, COVID 19.

Introduction

The COVID 19 pandemic was one of the scariest and stressful times for everyone throughout the globe. During these unprecedented times people have experienced mental stress and trauma with diverse context. There is no doubt, that it has affected our lives and changed us either increasing sensitivity in following the protocols, listening to new updates on controlling the signs and symptoms of pandemic, or bombarding the information of what to do and what not to. Globally, lots of people had lost their lives during COVID-19. The People at different life stages have faced their own set of specific challenges such as young children, adolescents, adults, older adults, and people with limitations in movement etc.

COVID-19 was declared as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) on 30 January 2020 by World Health Organization (WHO). As per the reports from WHO, the COVID19 pandemic was declared as the crucial case of human crisis with 6 million confirmed cases and 350,000 deaths reported globally up to May 31st 2020. A PHEIC is an acronym which represents public health emergency of international concern. PHEIC is basically a formal declaration of 'an extraordinary event which is determined to constitute a public health risk to other States through the international spread of disease and to potentially require a coordinated international response', formulated when a situation arises that is 'serious, sudden, unusual or unexpected', which 'carries implications for public health beyond the affected state's national border' and 'may require immediate international action'. States have a legal duty to respond promptly to a PHEIC. PHEICs can pose a remarkable mental health specifically to the population of developing countries where it can put them on risk from socio-economic status (Davis et al, 2010).

The global pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which was first identified in December 2019 in Wuhan, China. It is considered as the worst pandemic of the century in terms of incidence and number of deaths, if not the worst pandemic of the past 100 years. The effects of COVID-19 pandemic were horrifying and severely impacted the health and wellbeing of millions of people. Additionally, it had put an extreme toll on the mental and emotional health of the individuals as well and this consequently had a disastrous impact on the overall health system.

As we enter in adulthood, hardships and challenges somehow became the part of our lives. These challenging situations are inevitable and as we

grow older, eventually we also learn how to deal with them with time. Studies have suggested that these challenges and hardships can serve as opportunities for further growth and personal development (Resnick, Gwyther, & Roberto, 2010)

The concept of emerging adulthood is comparatively new and became popular from Western world. Emerging adults are specifically individuals in 18-25 years of their life and who have developmentally distinctive changes and experiences (Arnett, 2000). This age group has their unique set of challenges such as pursuing higher education, getting jobs, marrying early or postponing it for adding more to career goals, having or not having children etc. This trend is also very common to Indian population, therefore, being a majorly youth population country, researchers are quite excited to explore this concept in context our country.

In many western cultures, emerging adults (EAs) tend to postpone marriage, focus on higher education, and frequently change their living situations. This phase of life challenges traditional developmental expectations ((Arnett, 2006). During this time, they experience emotional growth (Reio & Sanders-Reio, 2020), build deeper personal and social connections, and solidify their political, academic, and career aspirations (Hochberg & Konner, 2020). Around age 25, significant brain changes occur—neurons are refined, white matter expands (Hochberg & Konner, 2020), and the frontal lobe completes its maturation. These transformations mark the shift from adolescence to adulthood (Meyer et al., 2019).

Emerging adults navigate the transition from youth to adulthood, facing key social milestones such as completing their education, entering the workforce, moving out of their parental home, forming romantic partnerships, and starting families (Billari & Liebroer, 2010).

The pandemic has intensified these challenges, making this transition even more difficult. While emerging adults are generally at lower risk for severe illness and mortality from COVID-19, their concerns about the present and future have led to increased stress, depression, and anxiety. Research, including both longitudinal (O'Connor et al., 2020) and cross-sectional (Glowacz & Schmits, 2020) studies, suggests that the pandemic has had a greater negative impact on the mental health and well-being of emerging adults compared to other age groups.

The COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent lockdown created an environment that heightened emotional distress. Shanahan et al (2020) conducted a longitudinal cohort study using data from both before and during the pandemic are necessary to accurately measure the changes in

emotional distress. They examined the emotional distress of 768 participants such as perceived stress, internalizing symptoms, and anger alongside pandemic-related stressors and coping strategies. These participants were measured when they were 22 years old, while their prior distress and stressors had been recorded at age 20. The results reflected on an average, participants experienced more stress and anger during the pandemic, but their levels of internalizing symptoms remained unchanged. Emotional distress from before the pandemic was the strongest predictor of distress during the crisis, followed by economic and social stressors, lifestyle disruptions, and feelings of hopelessness. Past social challenges like bullying and stressful life events also contributed. However, direct health risks from COVID-19 were not strongly linked to emotional distress in final analyses. Coping strategies that helped mitigate distress included maintaining daily routine, exercising, and reframing challenges in a positive light.

Angela et al (2022) conducted study to identify the available resources on resilience for emerging adults in order to manage the problems during the pandemic. The study was cross-national which included the 1768 respondents from various countries such as China, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovenia, and the US. The resilience dimensions addressed were ego-resiliency, positivity, religiosity, socioeconomic status, family support, peer support. The results of the in-depth profile analysis reflected four profiles of the respondents such as having no resources, only peer, only family, and well-equipped. These profiles were also associated with demographic variable, adulthood markers, self-perceived pandemic impact, present well-being.

Resilience is generally defined as bouncing back in the adverse conditions. Resilience is an active process where individuals learn to better adapt themselves in the times of uncertainty, stress, trauma, threats (Southwick & Charney, 2012). It is understood as fighting back, in the worst case scenario, we can also understand to survive in extremely unfavorable conditions. Resilience develops with the passage of time, more and more experience and exposed with threatening circumstances, therefore it is time-taking. Sisto *et al* (2019) explained resilience as a dynamic process which matures with time and seems to be adaptive in nature. It specifically exposes us with difficulty and we learn to face it by bouncing back as a chance to grow.

Although, there are multiple factors for understanding resilience, either considering it as a personality trait or learning and adapting with time. However, this research aims on exhibiting resilience in context of one's personality and strong social support from family and friends, especially focused during unprecedented times of COVID 19. Family is the foremost important institution to build the capacity to fight back with unfavorable conditions.

Kaye-Kauderer et al (2021) conducted a literature review where they explained the resilience as a complex and active process and tried to understand in context of genes, stress-response systems, beliefs, immune system, positive adaptations, and individual's deliberate response to unfavorable conditions. They also have taken the pandemic COVID-19 as a case example to better explain the individual and group responses towards uncertainty.

Barthélemy et al (2021) suggested evidence-based recommendations for the neurosurgeon and patient dyads as the interactions between the dyad impacts the overall well-being of both. They gathered empirical data and advised how to develop resilience for encouraging healthy and protective mechanisms which is quite effective in context of COVID 19.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered daily life, bringing uncertainty, insecurity, and instability—especially for young adults. While medical reports suggest that younger people are less likely to contract severe cases of COVID-19, emerging adults may be particularly vulnerable to the psychological impact of the pandemic. Many of them expressed greater concern about unknowingly spreading the virus rather than contracting it themselves.

Cultural factors such as individualism, collectivism, equality, and hierarchy play a role in how people perceive and cope with the pandemic. A study involving 1,183 young adults in Italy, conducted during the second week of the country's lockdown, found that participants had a strong understanding of COVID-19 but were more worried about the health of their relatives and society at large rather than their own well-being. Anxiety and stress levels were high, reflecting the difficulties young adults faced during this period (Germani et al., 2020).

Interestingly, Germani et al. (2020) found out that those with a collectivist mindset—emphasizing shared goals and interdependence—were more likely to perceive a higher risk of infection but showed lower levels of psychological distress. The study suggests that fostering social connections and promoting collective well-being could help mitigate the psychological effects of the pandemic among young adults.

van den Berg et al. (2021) conducted a study to examine how the mental health of young adults changed before and during the COVID-19 pandemic and whether support from parents and friends influenced these changes. Researchers followed 98 young adults over time, assessing them both before the pandemic (at an average age of 20.6) and during the first lockdown (at an average age of 22.67). The findings revealed that the pandemic did not universally worsen mental health. Instead, the effects varied based on individuals' pre-existing mental health and where they received support. Those who had more psychological distress before the pandemic benefited from maternal support, which helped reduce their anxiety and depression. However, paternal support appeared to be linked to increased distress. Meanwhile, support from close friends did not seem to significantly affect changes in mental health. This study suggested that the source of emotional support can play a complex role in shaping mental health outcomes during times of crisis. Understanding these dynamics could help improve mental health interventions and support systems for young adults in similar situations.

In 2022, Roberts et al. conducted a study on resilience and mental health experiences of emerging adults during the COVID 19 pandemic. This study explores the mental health effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on emerging adults from diverse communities, including those with disabilities, international students, and LGBTQ2AAI+ individuals. Given the limited research in this area, the study provides valuable insights. Researchers interviewed seven undergraduate students (ages 19–30) at a university in British Columbia, Canada, using a narrative-style approach over Zoom.

By analyzing their experiences through a resilience framework, the study found that participants faced varied challenges and adapted in different ways. The four key protective factors emerged during the data collection were: positive relationships, perceived efficacy, purpose and ambition, and sense of normality. The positive relationships protective factor considers support received from friends, family, and the community. The perceived efficacy factor includes the confidence of the emerging adults in their own ability to manage challenges. The next protective factor of purpose and ambition encompasses a strong sense of direction and motivation. The last protective element of sense of normality covers the maintenance of routines and familiar structures to foster stability during the crisis time. These findings contribute to the understanding of how diverse groups navigated the pandemic, offering guidance for university administrators and policymakers in improving mental health services and support systems. This research helps shape more inclusive and responsive strategies for the future (Roberts et al., 2022).

Social support encompasses emotional, informational, and practical assistance from significant individuals such as family, friends, or colleagues. This support may be directly received or simply perceived as available when needed (Thoits, 2010). It is a complex concept that reflects the extent to which individuals receive, feel, or require support. Regardless of the circumstances, research consistently indicates that social support plays a crucial role in promoting both physical and mental

well-being (Asberg et al., 2008; Cohen, 2004). Moreover, experiencing emotional closeness and support serves as a protective factor against the onset of mental health challenges.

Older teenagers and young adults may be especially vulnerable during this period of transition, as they shift from their inherited families to their chosen families, a process that can leave them without crucial support systems to help combat loneliness. College students may struggle with feelings of homesickness and difficulty fitting in, while those not in schools might feel disconnected from key social groups or communities. Additionally, young people often face important decisions about their careers, relationships, and personal lives, which can further contribute to stress and isolation during unprecedented times (Walsh & Walsh, 2023). Resilience in emerging adults during the pandemic can be shaped by their living situation—whether they are with their families or living independently. Those living with family may have access to emotional support, financial stability, and a sense of security that can help them cope with uncertainty. However, they may also experience challenges such as strained relationships or a loss of independence, which could impact their mental well-being.

On the other hand, emerging adults who are living away from family might face heightened feelings of loneliness and isolation, making resilience more crucial in maintaining their mental health. They often rely on friendships, chosen families, and personal coping strategies to navigate stress and uncertainty. This group may develop strong self-reliance and adaptability, which are key components of resilience.

Regardless of their living situation, factors such as social support, self-efficacy, and coping mechanisms play a significant role in fostering resilience among emerging adults during the pandemic. The ability to find meaning in challenges, maintain connections with loved ones, and seek professional or community support can all contribute to their ability to adapt and thrive. Therefore, the purpose of the present research study was to examine the idea of bouncing back capacity of the emerging adults in two scenarios while living with family and living independently.

Method

The study was conducted during pandemic, therefore the sample comprised of 36 emerging adults (18-25 years). The respondents were either pursuing higher education, who were staying in hostels due to lockdown or working professionals who were working from homes during COVID 19 lockdown. The living arrangement of the respondents was varied such as living either alone in hostel room, on rent and or with

Result

Table 1 Demographic profile of the sample

Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age		
18-20	12	33.34
21-23	14	38.88
24-25	10	27.78
Educational Attainment	4	11.11
High school	5	13.88
Intermediate	19	52.77
Undergraduate	5	13.88
Post-graduate	3	8.34
Ph.D.		
Marital Status		
Unmarried	20	55.55
Married	16	44.45
Student/working professional		
Student	19	52.77
Working professional	17	47.2367
Living arrangement during the study		
Alone (such as in hostel, apartment etc.)	21	58.34
With Family	15	41.66

their families. The snowball sampling method was used to select the participants for the present study, where participants recruited others in similar backgrounds that is, specifically who were meeting the criteria of age group and living arrangement during the lockdown. The participants were contacted through their mobile numbers, and they were thoroughly conveyed the purpose of the research study. The research made sure that the participants were meeting the criteria for the study through short telephonic conversation. Due to the protocols of the pandemic, the telephonic conversation was extremely helpful in filling out the demographic details of the respondents and understanding their experiences during the pandemic. After taking their consent, the research proceeded and the participants were asked to take the online BRS survey.

Socio-personal Information Sheet

The demographic data such age, marital status, living arrangement, working or studying, living either with family or alone etc. was collected by using self-prepared socio-personal information sheet. The Socio-personal Information Sheet comprises both open and closed ended questions and it was completed by the researcher.

Brief Resilience Scale BRS (Smith et al., 2008)

The resilience of the respondents was assessed through administering Brief Resilience Scale (Smith et al, 2008). This scale measures resilience by six statements which are based on capacity to bounce back, recovery, and time taken to recover etc. All the statements are answered using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

Procedure

The data was collected by using snowball sampling method by recruiting initiated through working professionals, students, and acquaintances who were contacted via telephone and after they gave their consent, were asked to complete the survey. They were also requested to forward the survey link to their acquaintances they know, who were in the same life stage of emerging adulthood. The data for this study was collected through quantitative technique using electronic (online) Survey Heart survey methods. It is fast and less time consuming, therefore participants could easily respond anytime according to their choice convenience and flexibility. Another important factor behind using electronically collecting data was to maintain the protocols for avoiding COVID 19. Prior to the survey the respondents were communicated about the research purpose, confidentiality status and contact information of the researcher.

Table 1 represents the items on a range of demographic characteristics, age, educational qualifications, marital status, profession, and lastly their living arrangements during the pandemic either living with their families or stuck alone due to lockdown. The respondents under study were the emerging adults (18-25 years) who were distributed into three sub age-groups such as 18-20, 21-23, and 24-25. The majority of participants were between the ages of 21 and 23, comprising 38.88% of the sample. Those aged 18 to 20 made up 33.34%, while individuals aged 24 to 25 accounted for 27.78%. More than half of the respondents (52.77%) were undergraduates. Participants with intermediate and post-graduate qualifications each represented 13.88% of the group. High school

graduates made up 11.11%, and 8.34% of the participants held a Ph.D. A slight majority of the participants (55.55%) were unmarried, while 44.45% were married. As far as the profession was concerned in which they were involved during the study, students formed the larger portion of the sample at 52.77%, whereas working professionals made up 47.24%. Lastly, the living arrangements of the respondents, most participants (58.34%) lived alone, such as in hostels or apartments, while 41.66% lived with their families during the study. The living arrangement of the respondents was based on the pandemic situation, whether they were living with their families or stuck alone during the lockdown.

Table 2 Per cent distribution of emerging adults as per levels of resilience during the pandemic

Level of Resilience	Frequency	Per cent
High	2	5.55
Medium	21	58.33
Low	7	36.11

NA: Not applicable

Table 2 represents the percent distribution of the respondents as per levels of resilience experienced during COVID 19 lockdown. The data on the level of resilience among participants reveals that the majority exhibited a moderate capacity to cope with stress and adversity. Specifically, 58.33% of the respondents fell into the medium resilience category, indicating that while they possess some adaptive coping mechanisms, there may still be room for growth in their ability to manage challenges effectively. Interestingly, the emerging adults who fall under medium level of resilience, majority of them were staying with their families. Being surrounded by loved ones helped buffer stress, anxiety, and uncertainty. Families provided a sense of safety and belonging in the challenging times. In India, spiritual rituals and community values holds higher place in individual's lives, therefore, these actions often reinforced hope and psychological endurance during lockdowns.

A significant portion—36.11%—were identified as having low resilience, suggesting that over one-third of the participants may struggle with stress management and could benefit from targeted support or interventions to build emotional strength and coping skills. Only a small fraction, 5.55%, demonstrated high resilience, reflecting a strong ability to bounce back from difficulties and maintain psychological well-being under pressure. This distribution highlights the importance of resilience-building programs, especially for those in the low to medium range, to enhance overall mental health and adaptive functioning.

Concluding, staying with family during COVID-19 generally made bouncing back capability better, especially when relationships were strong and communication was healthy. This resilience capacity also emerges due to internal satisfaction of being with your loved ones in the most challenging times of your life.

Discussion

The present study was conducted to observe the resilience among the emerging adults during unprecedented times. Resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic emerged as a vital psychological and social asset, helping individuals, communities, and organizations navigate unprecedented challenges. The pandemic brought about widespread uncertainty, isolation, and disruption, yet many people demonstrated remarkable adaptability and strength in the face of adversity.

The Mental Health Foundation found that 64% of people in the UK reported coping well with pandemic-related stress, often by engaging in activities like walking, spending time in nature, and staying connected with loved ones (*Resilience Across the UK During the Coronavirus Pandemic*, n.d.).

The pandemic revealed that resilience is not solely an internal trait but a dynamic process influenced by external factors such as social support, economic stability, and access to healthcare. It also emphasized the need

for systemic investment in mental health infrastructure, especially for vulnerable populations.

Family support plays a crucial role in shaping the emotional and psychological well-being of emerging adults, especially during periods of stress, transition, or adversity. When young individuals face challenges—whether academic pressure, career uncertainty, personal struggles, or unprecedented times like pandemic—a supportive family environment can act as a stabilizing force. Emotional encouragement, practical assistance, and a sense of belonging provided by family members help reduce feelings of isolation and anxiety, making it easier for individuals to cope with difficulties.

Supportive families foster a sense of psychological safety, where emerging adults feel understood, valued, and accepted. This emotional security enables them to process negative emotions more effectively and develop healthier coping mechanisms. When individuals know they have a reliable support system to fall back on, they are more likely to take constructive risks, seek help when needed, and recover more quickly from setbacks.

Family members often model adaptive coping strategies and problem-solving behaviors. Through observation and interaction, emerging adults learn how to manage stress, regulate emotions, and approach challenges with confidence. This nurtures a sense of self-efficacy—the belief in one's ability to overcome obstacles—which is a key component of resilience.

In times of crisis—such as financial hardship, academic failure, health issues, or uncertainty—family support can buffer the impact of external stressors. Practical help like financial assistance, guidance in decision-making, or simply being present can significantly reduce the burden on young adults, allowing them to focus on recovery and growth.

Words of encouragement and belief in one's potential from family members can be incredibly motivating. This emotional reinforcement boosts morale and helps individuals maintain a positive outlook, even in the face of adversity. Such optimism is strongly linked to greater resilience and better long-term outcomes.

The pandemic served as a global stress test for resilience, highlighting both the strengths and gaps in our individual and collective capacity to bounce back. Family support is not just a comforting presence—it is a powerful protective factor that enhances the capacity of emerging adults to bounce back from life's challenges. Strengthening family bonds and promoting open communication within households can be a vital strategy in building a more resilient generation.

Limitations

This study is subject to certain limitations that should be acknowledged. Firstly, the relatively small sample size may limit the generalizability of the findings. A larger and more diverse sample would provide greater

statistical power and enhance the reliability of the results across broader populations. Secondly, the study did not account for gender differences in the analysis. Given that resilience can be influenced by gender-related socialization, expectations, and coping styles, the absence of gender-based comparisons restricts the depth of interpretation. Future research should aim to include a more representative sample and incorporate gender as a key variable to better understand the nuanced ways in which resilience manifests across different demographic groups.

Implications

Understanding the factors that fostered resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic offers valuable insight for preparing society to face future crises—whether they stem from pandemics, climate disasters, or economic upheavals. One of the most critical lessons is the need for mental health systems to be agile and responsive. This means building infrastructure that can quickly adapt to emerging challenges, including scalable digital platforms for remote care, mobile crisis units that reach vulnerable populations, and rapid deployment of psychological first aid to support emotional recovery in real time. By integrating these strategies into public health planning, we can strengthen our collective resilience and ensure that mental well-being remains a priority in times of uncertainty.

Conclusion

The COVID-19 lockdown presented a profound psychological challenge for emerging adults, a group already navigating the complex transition from adolescence to adulthood. This study sought to assess the levels of resilience among individuals in this age group, with a particular focus on their living arrangements—whether residing with family or living alone. The findings suggest that living with family during the lockdown may have provided a protective buffer, offering emotional and practical support that contributed to higher resilience levels. In contrast, those living alone often faced increased isolation and stress, which may have hindered their ability to cope effectively with the disruptions caused by the pandemic.

While many participants demonstrated moderate resilience, the presence of low resilience in a significant portion of the sample highlights the need for targeted mental health interventions. The study underscores the critical role of family support in fostering emotional stability and adaptive coping mechanisms during crises. However, it also reveals that resilience is a multifaceted construct influenced by both internal traits and external circumstances. Future research should explore these dynamics further, incorporating larger and more diverse samples, and examining additional variables such as gender, socioeconomic status, and digital connectivity to gain a more comprehensive understanding of resilience in emerging adulthood.

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